

**THERMOELASTIC ASSESSMENT OF COMPOSITE DELAMINATION
BUCKLING**Cedric Antolis¹, Nik Rajic², Pier Marzocca¹, Raj Das¹¹ School of Engineering, RMIT University, GPO Box 2476, Melbourne, Victoria 3001, Australia
s3448276@student.rmit.edu.au² Aerospace Division, Defence Science and Technology Group, 506 Lorimer Street, Fishermans Bend,
Victoria, 3207, Australia.
Nik.Rajic@dst.defence.gov.au**Keywords:** thermoelastic stress analysis, delamination buckling, impact damage**ABSTRACT**

A quasi-isotropic IM7/977-3 laminate coupon containing a subsurface full-width artificially embedded delamination is subjected to uniaxial compressive loading to induce localised delamination buckling which is examined with thermoelastic stress analysis (TSA) using low-cost microbolometer imaging technology. Under a 10 kN load excursion in the post-buckling state, comparisons were made between strain imagery obtained from electronic speckle pattern interferometry (ESPI), discrete strain measurements obtained from electrical resistance strain gauges, and finite element model predictions as a baseline. While the TSA results varied with load frequency, at all considered frequencies TSA was found to yield significantly more accurate stress measurements in the region of buckling, compared to ESPI. TSA applied to the specimen under a stepwise loading regime identified a load threshold corresponding to the onset of elastic nonlinearity within the specimen's delamination zone. These results indicate a potential for this approach to be applied for the identification of load thresholds in impact damaged composites at which mechanisms promoting damage growth become significant.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have many advantages over traditional metallic alloys for aircraft construction, including vastly superior strength/stiffness-to-weight ratios, fatigue resistance, corrosion-resistance and potentially lower life-cycle costs [1]. One of their major downsides is poor damage tolerance. Owing to their layered structure, laminates have low through-thickness interlaminar shear strength [2] and impact resistance [3].

Most aircraft operate in environments in which low-velocity impacts causing barely visible impact damage (BVID) are commonplace. Such damage is by definition difficult to detect with the naked eye and may seriously degrade the stiffness and residual compressive strength of an affected structure. Due to the relatively low fracture toughness of the epoxy matrix, composites are prone to fatigue cracking under relatively low mode I interlaminar loads. When damaged composite structures are placed under compressive loads, delaminated outer sub-laminates tend to buckle locally, creating a mechanism for delamination propagation, potentially leading to failure. The durability of damaged composite structures under operational loads is still not fully understood. Traditionally, the design and certification of safety-critical composite components follows a no-growth philosophy underpinned by rigorous coupon, element and subcomponent testing [4].

Experimental analysis of composite buckling has typically involved measurement of surface strains via precision full-field optical measurement techniques such as Electronic speckle pattern interferometry (ESPI) [5], Digital Image Correlation [6,7] and Moiré techniques [8], as well as contact methods using Linear Variable Differential Transducers [9]. Full-field strain measurement techniques have known limitations. They rely on conversions of displacement gradients into strain, which are susceptible to measurement noise. In the case of DIC and ESPI, erroneous results have been reported for structures undergoing buckling or large displacement events [5,6].

This paper will present buckling analyses of a composite laminate containing an artificial delamination under uniaxial compressive loading using an approach based on thermoelastic stress analysis (TSA). The measured thermoelastic response within the local post-buckling state is compared with corresponding stress/strain measurements obtained from ESPI and stress/strain predictions obtained from finite element modelling. This measurement approach is used to quantify load thresholds at which significant localised stress increases in laminates occur when undergoing compression-compression cyclic loading. Such increases in stress are surmised to indicate mechanisms promoting damage growth, such as localised delamination buckling.

2 THERMOELASTIC STRESS ANALYSIS (TSA)

TSA is based on the thermoelastic effect, or Kelvin's law, which describes the relationship between the change in bulk stress and temperature under adiabatic conditions (1),

$$\frac{\Delta T}{T} = \frac{-\alpha}{\rho C_p} \Delta \sigma, \quad (1)$$

where ΔT is the change in temperature, T is absolute temperature, α is the coefficient of linear thermal expansion, ρ is the material density, C_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure, $\Delta \sigma$ is the change in bulk stress (sum of principal stresses). The theoretical basis and use of TSA for the inspection of composites is well established [10]. In orthotropic materials, such as unidirectional lamina, this relationship can be expressed in the following form (2) [11],

$$\Delta T = \frac{-T}{\rho C_p} (\alpha_1 \Delta \sigma_1 + \alpha_2 \Delta \sigma_2), \quad (2)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the directions parallel and transverse to the fibre, respectively. The interpretation of thermoelastic response measurements in composite materials is typically more challenging than in isotropic materials. The reasons include the difficulty in attaining adiabatic conditions in cross-ply laminates due to the presence of through-thickness stress discontinuity at cross-ply interfaces, and the complicating effects of fibre/matrix heterogeneity and surface resin layers.

3 DELAMINATION BUCKLING ANALYSIS OF LAMINATE CONTAINING ARTIFICIAL DELAMINATION

3.1 Specimen description and Experimental method

Coupons, 150 x 100 x 4 mm in size, were water-jet cut from panels manufactured using CYCOM IM7/977-3 pre-preg in a quasi-isotropic layup [45,0,0,-45,90]_{3S}. To manufacture a specimen containing an artificial delamination, a 40 x 100 mm strip of 0.001" thick Fluorinated Ethylene Propylene (FEP) release-film was embedded between plies four and five during the layup process before curing. This strip was centred and spans the full width of the coupon, as shown in Figure 1. Prior to experimental analysis, these specimens were exposed to short duration low uniaxial compression loads to ensure no residual adhesion between plies at the insert location. This was subsequently confirmed via microscopic examination and phased array ultrasonic testing. Coupons were painted with high emissivity Krylon khaki paint, and secured in a Wyoming Test Fixtures ASTM D 7137 anti-buckling fixture installed in a 100 kN MTS servo-hydraulic test machine.

Figure 1: Cross sectional diagram and photo of unpainted specimen showing location of FEP insert between ply 4 and ply 5.

Figure 2: Photo of experimental setups for TSA (left) and ESPI (right).

2D ESPI measurements were obtained using a Dantec Dynamics Q-300 system (Figure 2). The specimen was loaded in uniaxial compression, from 25 to 35 kN in 30 \sim 0.33 kN increments. This step size was determined by experimental investigation to produce the highest quality strain imagery, i.e. it was large enough to produce sufficient fringe contrast and density, but without causing severe speckle decorrelation. The strain image for the entire load excursion was obtained through cumulative summation of resultant strain fields at each step, automatically calculated by the Dantec ISTR software. Estimations for stress were made based on a computationally derived elastic modulus of 70.41 GPa, calculated using published material properties and the equivalent single layer theory of laminates

[12]. Longitudinal strain measurements were taken on the specimen at each load using two strain gauges (Kyowa, 120 Ohm, 2.11 Gauge Factor) mounted at the centre of the delamination and in the lower far-field, respectively.

For TSA, the specimen was subjected to uniaxial compression-compression cyclic loading between 25 and 35 kN, at frequencies in the range: 1-18 Hz. Two Xenics Gobi 640 microbolometers facing the front and back of the specimen (Figure 2) streamed raw infrared video into laptops running MiTE software, which computes the in-phase (proportional to bulk stress) and quadrature components of the thermoelastic response [13]. The observation time was approximately 15 minutes for each test frequency.

3.2 Finite Element Model

For further comparison, a 3D geometrically non-linear model was created using the COMSOL Multiphysics 5.4 software package. The coupon was modelled using layered shell elements and material properties obtained from the literature [11]. Three mesh elements per ply thickness were used for the top four plies, which are expected to undergo buckling in the delamination zone, while the remaining plies were modelled together under an equivalent single-layer assumption containing four mesh elements through thickness. A thin elastic layer interface was used to model the delamination caused by the FEP insert. Mesh refinements were made in the delamination zone (Figure 3). The boundary conditions reflected the physical restraint provided by the anti-buckling fixture. Left and right sides were restricted from moving in the out-of-plane (Z) direction and top and bottom were set as rigid connectors with the bottom constrained in the longitudinal (Y) direction. Uniform compressive forces of 25 and 35 kN were applied to the top surface. To facilitate buckling, a small eccentricity was introduced to the structure via a 10 N outwards pulling force on the delamination interface.

Figure 3: Mesh and boundary conditions used in FE model.

3.3 Results and Discussion

Figure 4: (a) Longitudinal stress (MPa) as obtained from ESPI, corresponding to a change in load from -25 to -35 kN, and (b) FE model prediction of the change in 1st strain invariant for the same load change.

Figure 5: In-phase thermoelastic response images for a change in load from -25 to -35 kN (cyclic) at 1, 3 and 10 Hz. The scale on the right is in arbitrary units with negative values indicate a compressive stress and positive values a tensile stress.

Figure 6: Line plot A-B normalised to the averaged signal in the undamaged region. Signal values represent the in-phase response for TSA, change in bulk stress for ESPI, change in 1st strain invariant for FEM and change in longitudinal strain for the strain gauges.

Visual comparisons between ESPI, FEM and TSA show similarity and suggest a consistent, symmetrical local-buckling mode shape in which there is a transition between increasing compressive stress into an increasing tensile stress towards the centre of the delamination. Quantitative comparisons between all the results were made through taking vertical line plots approximately 60 mm in length in the centre, encompassing both the undamaged section and the delamination area (shown by line AB in Figure 6). Each plot was normalised to the average value in the undamaged section. In general, a greater contrast and a stronger thermoelastic response were seen with an increase in frequency. While the TSA response at all frequencies was able to characterise the local buckling behaviour, scans at the lowest frequency of 1 Hz, showed a washed out response with less detail and contrast in areas where there are large in-plane stress gradients. The frequency dependence of the TSA results can be attributed to heat diffusion effects, which grow significantly with decreasing frequency. As already outlined, the large through-thickness stress discontinuities in cross ply laminates under load is a factor in this effect. These frequency dependent effects will be considered in a subsequent study in which geometrically non-linear thermo-elastically coupled modelling will be undertaken.

Initially, the transverse strain distribution measured by ESPI was found to be erroneous and noisy, even after phase filtering was applied. The longitudinal component was also found to be almost a factor of 5 greater than the corresponding strain gage measurement. This is attributed to known limitations of ESPI in measuring strains in structures undergoing large buckling deformations, as has previously been discussed in the literature [5]. Subsequently the transverse strain distribution was calculated from the longitudinal distribution using a Poisson's ratio indicated by FEM.

3.4 Investigation of buckling onset using TSA

TSA was next applied to the specimen described above under a sinusoidal loading which was increased in amplitude incrementally. The aim was to identify the threshold load amplitude at which non-linear behaviour commences in the delamination zone. The TSA measurements were made using the experimental configuration described in section 3.1. The coupon was subjected to a uniaxial compression-compression cyclic loading of constant amplitude, a stress ratio $R=10$ and at discrete frequencies of 1, 3, 5 and 10 Hz. The maximum compressive load was increased in 5 kN increments from 10 kN up to a maximum value of 60 kN. TSA measurements were taken at each load for a sufficient duration to ensure a satisfactory signal-to-noise ratio, ~15 mins.

Figure 7: In-phase thermoelastic images at 3 Hz for different load maximums. The scale is as described for Figure 5.

Figure 7 shows a representative set of in-phase thermoelastic response measurements as a function of the load maximum for the 3 Hz case. The appearance of a strong bipolar signature at the higher loads signifies a transition from linear to non-linear behaviour in the region of the delamination.

A more detailed quantitative analysis of the TSA results was undertaken by plotting the in-phase thermoelastic response amplitude averaged in a circle ~10 pixels in radius, at two locations, one in the far field and the other centered on the delamination, with the results shown in Figure 8. For brevity, only the in-phase component is shown, which is sufficient to illustrate the behaviour under investigation in this study. In the absence of non-linear elastic deformation, the bulk stress in the specimen is expected to increase linearly as a function of applied compressive load. Under adiabatic conditions, this should result also in a linear relationship between load and the in-phase thermoelastic response amplitude. This is reflected by the linear trend observed in the plots corresponding to the far field location. At the delamination, deviations from linearity are seen after ~25 kN at 3, 5, and 10 Hz, and at ~30 kN for the 1 Hz loading. It is surmised that this non-linearity is a result of the appearance of a flexural stress component generated by localised delamination buckling. This flexural component was seen to dominate after 40 kN, as confirmed by the positive in-phase signal value, which indicates a net tensile stress. The higher load value at transition for the 1 Hz result is attributed to greater influence of diffusion at this frequency.

Figure 8: In-Phase thermoelastic response vs maximum load for centre region and far field at 1,3,5 and 10 Hz

9 CONCLUSION

An experimental investigation of a composite laminate coupon undergoing local post-buckling using low-cost microbolometer technology has demonstrated that TSA provides full-field stress estimates which more closely match FEM predictions and strain-gauge measurements than full-field measurements obtained from ESPI. This TSA approach has also been shown to be effective in determining the onset of stress non-linearity for buckling analysis, highlighting the potential for this technique to provide a practical means of identifying threshold loads at which non-linear deformation consistent with mode I damage growth occurs. This type of analysis may provide useful insight into the potential for growth of impact damage in composites under compressive loading. The results of this study also highlight some limitations of TSA, including a frequency dependence which stems from the large inter-ply temperature gradients caused by through thickness stress discontinuities, and intra-ply gradients caused by buckling. An investigation is currently underway to develop appropriate corrections for this effect in the analysis. An extension of this analysis approach to real impact damage is also underway.

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